

THE IMPORTANCE OF MULTIMEDIA IN EDUCATIONAL CONTEXTS

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Abstract: The article gives information about the ways to use technological developments, precisely multimedia including visuals, audio, animation in efficient ways to boost educational system of the country. The current article carries methods that are inter-related to technology and important to conduct lessons effectively.

Keywords: multimedia, elements, image, graphics

Introduction: In the XXI century, multimedia appliance in any field is considered one of the productive ways to improve the field. The growth of use of multimedia has increased drastically in recent years. To fulfill the needs of their students, teachers must have access to learning tools that may help them develop concepts in a variety of ways. Individual learning requirements The advancement of multimedia learning technologies provides new avenues for learning.

Research Method: Before touching the core task of the paper, it is appropriate to define several terms. What is multimedia itself? Through audio, visual, and animation accompaniment, multimedia pushes students to learn new languages. It also aids in the creation of English settings, as expanding one's grammar, vocabulary, and knowledge of pragmatics and genres is a crucial component of learning a language. Multimedia content combines several content forms such as video, 3D animation, photos, text, audio, and interactive information. It encourages students to study by using audio, video, and 3D animation. Multimedia is a fantastic technique to communicate because it is simple to communicate and understand what others are saying. During the lesson, any kind of information or theme that teacher finds difficult to explain, they can use the multimedia elements to finish their mission for the day. According to Mukherjee S., they are typically used for the sole intention of learning and teaching Regardless of personal preference. There are numerous definitions, but it is generally acknowledged that multimedia is classed as any blend of text, graphics, sound, animation, and video. *"In general, multimedia has been relatively successful because it draws upon more than one of the five human senses, utilizing the two fundamental senses vital for information reception – sight and sound"* (Mukherjee S., 2018).

Text and images are examples of multimedia elements and graphics, as well as audio, video, and animation texts, photos, and video. Three aspects of graphics are static (do not move), whilst the other three elements are moving objects or audio, video, and animations within a multimedia program, a dynamic object. *"Text is very important for communication in any medium. It involves the use of text types, sizes, colors and background colors. In a multimedia application, other media or screen can be linked through the use of text"* (Mukherjee S., 2018). Text can be created directly in an authoring application or imported from external text files. Text formats include ASCII/Unicode, HTML, Postscript, PDF, Note, and Word Pad.

Image and graphics. Graphics enhance the appeal of the multimedia application. They contribute to Still images are used to illustrate ideas. Graphics are classified into two categories bitmaps (paint graphics) and vectors were used (draw graphics). Bitmap images are actual images that can be acquired by equipment like cameras or scanners.

Audio. The best approach to attract attention is with audio. Speech, music, and sound effects may be required. These are the referred to as audio or the sound element to pique the interest of audience. Audio is useful for training and educational purposes. Analog audio and digital audio are the two forms of audio relates to the sound reproduction and transmission in digital format Sound or music digitization and storage on a computer or compact disc.

Animation: Animation is the process of making a static image appear to move. Digital animation is used in multimedia. Digital animation is divided into two categories: 2D (2 Dimension) animations and 3D (3 Dimension) animations. 2D animation is the process of animating basic objects. These objects are placed in various circumstances or positions and move across the screen. 3D animation is the process of animating three-dimensional digital objects created from pictures. Animations include movements such as whirling and flying across the screen. Because animations typically incorporate visuals, their size and file format are heavily reliant on the graphics being animated.

Analysis and Conclusion: Gaining productivity within the help of multimedia requires varied and proper selection of materials. These products and services should be selected according to the learners age and thinking as well as his knowledge in the field. Graphical views, images and all other elements are great force to make education and educating even more interesting and enjoyable. *“Allow students to function as designers, using tools or software for analyzing the words, accessing and interpreting information, organizing their personal knowledge” (Mukherjee S., 2018).* The ultimate goal of using variable multimedia elements during lesson is to promote students’ motivation and interest towards the subject. In the future, the ESL students will take the advantages of multimedia in the process of English learning and this method is more student-centered and less time-consuming. Therefore, it promises that teaching quality will be developed and through that students’ communicative competence will be further improved. To conclude, we believe that this process can completely improve students' ideation and practical language skills, which is beneficial and useful in ensuring and fulfilling an effective result of teaching and learning.

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